

Supplementary Information

Exosome-transmitted miR-224-5p Regulates Cell Proliferation via Intercellular Communication by Targeting ULK2 in Colorectal Cancer

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Supplementary Figures

Figure S1. A-E microarray analysis of miR-224-5p expression related to tumors based on sex (A), age (y, B), size (C), position (D) and lymphatic invasion (E). Data are shown as the ratio of signal of miR-224-5p of colorectal cancer tissues normalized with the signal value of miR-224-5p of normal tissues. ns means no significance (Student's t-test).

Figure S2. miR-224-5p promotes CRC cell proliferation. **A and B** Expression of miR-224-5p in HCT116 (A) and DLD1 (B) cells 48h after transfection with miR-224-5p mimic/inhibitor and miR-NC by qRT-PCR. **C and D** CCK-8 assays were conducted to detect cell viability 48h after transfection with miR-224-5p mimic/inhibitor and miR-NC in HCT116 (C) and DLD1 (D) cells. Data are shown as mean \pm SD (n = 3). * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$ & *** $p < 0.001$ vs. NC (Student's t-test). **E and F** Representative images of Hoechst⁺ cells, EdU⁺ cells and overlay 48h after transfection with miR-224-5p mimic/inhibitor and miR-NC in HCT116 (E) and DLD1 (F) cells, using 40 \times objective lens. **G and H** The ratio of the number of EdU⁺ cells to the number of Hoechst⁺ cells 48h after transfection with miR-224-5p mimic/inhibitor and miR-NC in HCT116 (G) and DLD1 (H) cells. Data are shown as mean \pm SD (n = 3). * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$ & *** $p < 0.001$ vs. NC (Student's t-test).

DLD1		309 site	
Query 1	TTCTCTTTGGCTGGGAGAGGAGCTGCTGTTGTTGCTAGTGCTAGGAAAAGGCAAGG	60	
Sbjct 327	TTCTCTTTGGCTGGGAGAGGAGCTGCTGTTGTTGCTAGTGCTAGGAAAAGGCAAGG	268	
Query 61	AAAGGTGATAAAAGTGAATCTGAGGCATAACTGCACCOCTGGTCTOCTCCACOGCTTCTT	120	
Sbjct 267	AAAGGTGATAAAAGTGAATCTGAGGCATAACTGCACCOCTGGTCTOCTCCACOGCTTCTT	208	
Query 121	GTOCTGCTTGCTTAOCTCGCTTAGTGCTCOCTGGGGCAGCTCGTGGTGAGGCTOCCCTT	180	
Sbjct 207	GTOCTGCTTGCTTAOCTCGCTTAGTGCTCOCTGGGGCAGCTCGTGGTGAGGCTOCCCTT	148	
Query 181	TCTTGGGAGATTCTTCTTCTGTCGGCCGCTCTTCCAGGACAGGCACAAAACCTCCA	240	
Sbjct 147	TCTTGGGAGATTCTTCTTCTGTCGGCCGCTCTTCCAGGACAGGCACAAAACCTCCA	88	
Query 241	CCTCAAAGCTGTTCCGTCCAGTAGATTA	269	273 site
Sbjct 87	CCTCAAAGCTGTTCCGTCCAGTAGATTA	59	

HCT116		309 site	
Query 1	TTCTCTTTGGCTGGGAGAGGAGCTGCTGTTGTTGCTAGTGCTAGGAAAAGGCAAGG	60	
Sbjct 327	TTCTCTTTGGCTGGGAGAGGAGCTGCTGTTGTTGCTAGTGCTAGGAAAAGGCAAGG	268	
Query 61	AAAGGTGATAAAAGTGAATCTGAGGCATAACTGCACCOCTGGTCTOCTCCACOGCTTCTT	120	
Sbjct 267	AAAGGTGATAAAAGTGAATCTGAGGCATAACTGCACCOCTGGTCTOCTCCACOGCTTCTT	208	
Query 121	GTOCTGCTTGCTTAOCTCGCTTAGTGCTCOCTGGGGCAGCTCGTGGTGAGGCTOCCCTT	180	
Sbjct 207	GTOCTGCTTGCTTAOCTCGCTTAGTGCTCOCTGGGGCAGCTCGTGGTGAGGCTOCCCTT	148	
Query 181	TCTTGGGAGATTCTTCTTCTGTCGGCCGCTCTTCCAGGACAGGCACAAAACCTCCA	240	
Sbjct 147	TCTTGGGAGATTCTTCTTCTGTCGGCCGCTCTTCCAGGACAGGCACAAAACCTCCA	88	
Query 241	CCTCAAAGCTGTTCCGTCCAGTAGATTA	269	273 site
Sbjct 87	CCTCAAAGCTGTTCCGTCCAGTAGATTA	59	

SW480		P309S	
Query 1	TTCTCTTTGGCTGGGAGAGGAGCTGCTGTTGTTGCTAGTGCTAGGAAAAGGCAAGG	60	
Sbjct 327	TTCTCTTTGGCTGGGAGAGGAGCTGCTGTTGTTGCTAGTGCTAGGAAAAGGCAAGG	268	
Query 61	AAAGGTGATAAAAGTGAATCTGAGGCATAACTGCACCOCTGGTCTOCTCCACOGCTTCTT	120	
Sbjct 267	AAAGGTGATAAAAGTGAATCTGAGGCATAACTGCACCOCTGGTCTOCTCCACOGCTTCTT	208	
Query 121	GTOCTGCTTGCTTAOCTCGCTTAGTGCTCOCTGGGGCAGCTCGTGGTGAGGCTOCCCTT	180	
Sbjct 207	GTOCTGCTTGCTTAOCTCGCTTAGTGCTCOCTGGGGCAGCTCGTGGTGAGGCTOCCCTT	148	
Query 181	TCTTGGGAGATTCTTCTTCTGTCGGCCGCTCTTCCAGGACAGGCACAAAACCTCCA	240	
Sbjct 147	TCTTGGGAGATTCTTCTTCTGTCGGCCGCTCTTCCAGGACAGGCACAAAACCTCCA	88	
Query 241	CCTCAAAGCTGTTCCGTCCAGTAGATTA	269	R273H
Sbjct 87	CCTCAAAGCTGTTCCGTCCAGTAGATTA	59	

HT29		309 site	
Query 1	TTCTCTTTGGCTGGGAGAGGAGCTGCTGTTGTTGCTAGTGCTAGGAAAAGGCAAGG	60	
Sbjct 327	TTCTCTTTGGCTGGGAGAGGAGCTGCTGTTGTTGCTAGTGCTAGGAAAAGGCAAGG	268	
Query 61	AAAGGTGATAAAAGTGAATCTGAGGCATAACTGCACCOCTGGTCTOCTCCACOGCTTCTT	120	
Sbjct 267	AAAGGTGATAAAAGTGAATCTGAGGCATAACTGCACCOCTGGTCTOCTCCACOGCTTCTT	208	
Query 121	GTOCTGCTTGCTTAOCTCGCTTAGTGCTCOCTGGGGCAGCTCGTGGTGAGGCTOCCCTT	180	
Sbjct 207	GTOCTGCTTGCTTAOCTCGCTTAGTGCTCOCTGGGGCAGCTCGTGGTGAGGCTOCCCTT	148	
Query 181	TCTTGGGAGATTCTTCTTCTGTCGGCCGCTCTTCCAGGACAGGCACAAAACCTCCA	240	
Sbjct 147	TCTTGGGAGATTCTTCTTCTGTCGGCCGCTCTTCCAGGACAGGCACAAAACCTCCA	88	
Query 241	CCTCAAAGCTGTTCCGTCCAGTAGATTA	269	R273H
Sbjct 87	CCTCAAAGCTGTTCCGTCCAGTAGATTA	59	

 Wild-type Mutation

Figure S3. DNA sequencing validation was conducted to detect p53 gene mutation in codon 273 and 309 of CRC cells. The sequences above (Query) represent the result of sequencing and the sequences below (Sbjct) represent the p53 gene sequence in the NCBI database. R273H: a G → A mutation in codon 273 resulting in an Arg → His substitution; P309S: a C → T mutation in codon 309 resulting in a Pro → Ser substitution.

Figure S4. Exogenous miR-224-5p partially reverses the regulation effect of ULK2 on CRC cell proliferation. **A and B** CCK-8 assays were conducted to detect cell viability after transfection with miR-224-5p mimic/miR-NC in ULK2-overexpressed DLD1 (A) and SW480 (B) cells. Data are shown as mean \pm SD (n = 3). $**p < 0.01$ vs. LV-NC+miR-NC; $*p < 0.05$ & $**p < 0.01$ vs. LV-ULK2+miR-NC (Student's t-test). **C and D** Representative images of Hoechst⁺ cells, EdU⁺ cells and overlay after transfection with miR-224-5p mimic/ miR-NC in ULK2-overexpressed DLD1 (C) and SW480 (D) cells, using 20 \times objective lens. **E and F** The ratio of the number of EdU⁺ cells to the number of Hoechst⁺ cells after transfection with miR-224-5p mimic/miR-NC in ULK2-overexpressed DLD1 (E) and SW480 (F) cells. Data are shown as mean \pm SD (n = 3). $**p < 0.01$ vs. LV-NC+miR-NC; $*p < 0.05$ & $**p < 0.01$ vs. LV-ULK2+miR-NC (Student's t-test).

Supplementary Tables

Table S1. The clinical-pathological features of 66 cases CRC patients for microarray

Characteristics		Case (n)
Sex	Male	38
	Female	28
Age (y)	≤60	30
	>60	36
Tumor position	Colon	38
	Rectum	24
	Colorectal junction	4
Tumor Size	≤3cm	25
	>3cm	41
Tumor stage	Dukes' A	15
	Dukes' B	21
	Dukes' C	17
	Dukes' D	11
p53 status	Negative	18
	Positive	38
	Unknown	10
Lymphatic invasion	No	41
	Yes	25
Ki67	≤50%	22
	>50%	34
	Unknown	10

Table S2. The clinical-pathological features of 5 cases CRC patients for ULK2 immunohistochemistry analysis

No.	Sex	Age (y)	Histologic Type	Lymphatic Invasion	TNM
1	Male	46	Adenocarcinoma	Present	T3N1bM0
2	Male	52	Adenocarcinoma	Present	T2N1aM0
3	Female	67	Adenocarcinoma	Absent	T1N0M0
4	Male	57	Adenocarcinoma	Present	T2N2aM0
5	Female	69	Adenocarcinoma	Absent	T3N0M0

Table S3. The primer sequences used in this study

Target	Primer Sequences
GAPDH (human)	Forward: 5'-CTGACTTCAACAGCGACACC-3' Reverse: 5'-TGCTGTAGCCAAATTCGTTGT-3'
ULK2 (human)	Forward: 5'-ACAGCAAAGGAATCATCCACAG-3' Reverse: 5'-TGATGCGAATACCACTGACAC-3'
p53 (human)	Forward: 5'-AATCTACTGGGACGGAACAGC-3' Reverse: 5'-CCAAGACTTAGTACCTGAAGGGTG-3'
U6 (human)	Forward: 5'-GGAACGATACAGAGAAGATTAGC-3' Reverse: 5'-TGGAACGCTTCACGAATTTGCG-3'
miR-224-5p (human)	Forward: produced by Ribobio Reverse: Universal reverse sequence of the kit

Table S4. The sequences inserted in the pmirGLO to reconstruct ULK2 3'UTR-WT or ULK2 3'UTR-MUT plasmid

Names of inserts	Inserted sequences (5'→3')
ULK2 3'UTR-WT	<u>GTTTAAAC</u> CGTCCGCTGTGTGCCCCGGGGGCGCGGCCATGG AGGTGGTGG GTGACTT CGAGTACAGCAAGAGGGATCTCGT GGGACACGGGGCCTTCGTCTAGA
ULK2 3'UTR-MUT	<u>GTTTAAAC</u> CGTCCGCTGTGTGCCCCGGGGGCGCGGCCATGG AGGTGGTGG GCATGCG CGAGTACAGCAAGAGGGATCTCGT GGGACACGGGGCCTTCGTCTAGA

Notes: restriction sites are in underline; wild-type or mutant seed regions are in red.

Table S5. DNA reverse sequencing results of p53 gene in CRC cells

CRC cell line	Sequencing results
DLD1	NNNNNNCNNNNNNGGNTTCTTCTTTGGCTGGGGAGAGGAGCTGGTG TTGTTGGGCAGTGCTAGGAAAGAGGCAAGGAAAGGTGATAAAAGT GAATCTGAGGCATAACTGCACCCTTGGTCTCCTCCACCGCTTCTTGT CCTGCTTGCTTACCTCGCTTAGTGCTCCCTGGGGGCAGCTCGTGGTG AGGCTCCCCTTTCTTGCGGAGATTCTCTTCCTCTGTGCGCCGGTCTCT CCCAGGACAGGCACAAACACGCACCTCAAAGCTGTTCCGTCCCAGT AGATTA
HCT116	NNNNNNNNNNCNTNNNNNGGTTTCTTCTTTGGCTGGGGAGAGGAGCT GGTGTGTTGGGCAGTGCTAGGAAAGAGGCAAGGAAAGGTGATAA AAGTGAATCTGAGGCATAACTGCACCCTTGGTCTCCTCCACCGCTTC TTGTCCTGCTTGCTTACCTCGCTTAGTGCTCCCTGGGGGCAGCTCGT GGTGAGGCTCCCCTTTCTTGCGGAGATTCTCTTCCTCTGTGCGCCGG TCTCTCCAGGACAGGCACAAACACGCACCTCAAAGCTGTTCCGTCC CAGTAGATTA
SW480	NNNNNNNNNTNNNNNGTTCCTTCTTTGGCTGGGGAGAGGAGCTGGTG TTGTTGGACAGTGCTAGGAAAGAGGCAAGGAAAGGTGATAAAAGT GAATCTGAGGCATAACTGCACCCTTGGTCTCCTCCACCGCTTCTTGT CCTGCTTGCTTACCTCGCTTAGTGCTCCCTGGGGGCAGCTCGTGGTG AGGCTCCCCTTTCTTGCGGAGATTCTCTTCCTCTGTGCGCCGGTCTCT CCCAGGACAGGCACAAACATGCACCTCAAAGCTGTTCCGTCCCAGT AGATTA
HT29	NNNNNNNNNTNNGNNGNTTCTTCTTTGGCTGGGGAGAGGAGCTGGT GTTGTTGGGCAGTGCTAGGAAAGAGGCAAGGAAAGGTGATAAAAG TGAATCTGAGGCATAACTGCACCCTTGGTCTCCTCCACCGCTTCTTG TCCTGCTTGCTTACCTCGCTTAGTGCTCCCTGGGGGCAGCTCGTGGT GAGGCTCCCCTTTCTTGCGGAGATTCTCTTCCTCTGTGCGCCGGTCTC TCCAGGACAGGCACAAACATGCACCTCAAAGCTGTTCCGTCCCAG TAGATTA